

ARXAIZMLARNING HOZIRGI ADABIYOTI MUHITIDA TUTGAN O'RNI VA ROLI

To'xtamurodova Hanifa Dilmurodovna

BuxDU Pedagogika instituti talabasi

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ANNOTATSIYA: Arxaizmlar eski davr muhitiga o'quvchini olib kirish, tarixiy davrni gavdalantirish uchun foydalaniladi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'zbek tili leksikasi, arxaizmlar, zamonaviy adabiyot.

Tarixiylik jihatidan o'zbek tili leksikasi

1. eskirgan qatlam,
2. yangi qatlam,
3. zamonaviy qatlam(neologizmlar) ga bo'linadi.

Til tizim sifatida uzluksuz harakatda va rivojlanishda bo'lib turadi. Bu uning ijtimoiy mahiyatidan kelib chiqadi: til va jamiyat, til va ong, til va tafakkur o'rtasidagi ikki taraflama aloqadorlik ularning bir-biriga ta'sirini belgilaydi – jamiyatda bo'lib turadigan ijtimoiy-siyosiy o'zgarishlar, ilmiy-texnikaviy taraqqiyot, iqtisodiy va ma'rifiy sohadagi islohotlar, tilning lug'at boyligida yangi-yangi so'zlar va atamalarning yuzaga kelishini lekin ayni damda ma'lum so'z va leksemalarning eskirib, tarixiy kategoriyaga aylanishini taqozo qiladi. Bu jarayon tilning lug'at boyligida istorizm, arxaizm, neologizm kabi yangi til birliklarini yuzaga keltiradi. Eskirgan qatlam o'z ichida yana ikki guruhga arxaizmlar va istorizmlarga bo'linadi. Arxarizm yunoncha ko'hna, qadimgi degan ma'nolarni anglatadi. Bu atama avvallari tilimizda mavjud bo'lgan, ammo bugungi kunda iste'molda boshqacha nom bilan ishlatiladigan atama, so'zlarga nisbatan qo'llaniladi. Zamon va odamlar hayoti, turmush tarzi o'zgargan sayin arxaizmlar ko'payib boraveradi. Arxaizm o'z o'rnini boshqa leksemaga bo'shatib bergan leksik birlik.

Ijtimoiy taraqqiyot natijasida ayrim narsa-hodisa boshqa leksema bilan atalib, avvalgilari iste'moldan chiqib ketadi. Arxaik leksema o'zining neytral leksika tarkibidagi "o'rinbosar"ining "tarixiylik bo'yog'i" ifoda sememasi bilan farqlanuvchi sinonimdir. Tilda bõladigan õzgarish uzoq

vaqt davom etadigan tadrijiy jarayon. Shu boisdan yangi leksema tilga birdan kirib kelmaganligi kabi leksemaning tarixiylashuvi va arxaiklashuvi ham asta-sekinlik bilan yuz beradi. Shu boisdan tarixiylashish va arxaiklashish hodisasini ham darajalash mumkin. Tarixiylik yoki arxaiklashishning quyi darajasidagi leksema tilning bugungi bosqichida kam bõlsa ham, iste'molda bo'lsa, yuqori darajadagi eskirish natijasida leksema butkul iste'moldan chiqib ketadi.

Arxaizmlarga misollar: Oyoq-qadah, ulus-xalq, tilmoch-tarjimon, dudoq-lab, uzor-yuz, meng-xol. Ushbu so'zlar tilimizda bir necha asrlar oldin boshqacha ko'rinishda bo'lgan.

Bugungi kunda esa so'z o'zgarib tushuncha saqlangan hisoblanadi.

Zamonaviy adabiyotda arxaizmlardan kitobxonlarni o'sha muhitga yaqinlashtirish, davrda olib kirish, qahramonlar xarakterini to'liq ochib berish maqsadida qo'llaniladi. Arxaizmlar qo'llangan asarlardan parchalar:

1. Uyda oyimning maneken dugonalari, dadamning do'stlarining dastidan oyoq bosgani joy qolmaydi. Amina Shenliko'g'li "Imomning maneken qizi" asaridan. Parchadagi maneken so'zi hozirda modeler tarzida qo'llaniladi.

2. Moskovdan ishlangan pullaringniyam chiqarib ol! Iqbol Mirzo "Bonu". Parchadagi Moskov shahri nomi Moskva o'rnida ishlatiladi.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni ta'kidlash joizki, arxaizmlar adabiyotimizda o'z o'rniga ega va ularni o'rganish lozim.

Ushbu maqolada ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУҒАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолилик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris "Devonu lugotit turk" in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

Мамлакатимиз тараққиётининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

⁵ Bakhriddinova, B. M. (2020). "DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK" AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.⁹

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹⁰

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⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

⁹ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

¹⁰ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.

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